

Electrochemical behaviour of 3-[4'-(thiazolyl); 3-[4'-(acetyl)sulphonamoylphenyl] azomethineindoles

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Electrochemical behaviour of 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindoles was studied in Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 12.0 at glassy carbon (gc) electrode. Cyclic voltammograms exhibited a well defined irreversible $2e^-/2H^+$ cathodic peak below pH 7.9. At and above pH 7.9 one additional $2e^-/2H^+$ reduction peak was observed which was assigned to the reduction of C-N bond. Products of cpe was characterised by elemental and spectral analysis.

Electrochemical studies on sulpha drugs can provide unique insight into their redox behaviour in animal metabolism. Mayer *et al.*¹ has postulated that sulpha drugs undergo redox reactions in human metabolism resulting in the formation of different products that may be responsible for their bacteriostatic action. In the present study the azomethine group (-CH=N-) has been introduced in sulpha drug moiety. The -C=N- group occurs in many organic molecules of fundamental importance.

Azomethine ylids have been used for the synthesis of monoacids^{2,3}. Zuman and coworkers⁴ have studied the difference between the reactivity of azomethine bonds in metamitron in electrochemical and chemical reduction. Krishnamoorthy *et al.* have studied the electroreduction of Schiff bases at graphite electrode⁵. The azomethine products of (*R*)- α -methylhistamine have shown to be potent histamine H₃ receptor⁶. Several Schiff base complexes of transition metals have been synthesised and studied at different electrodes⁷⁻⁹. Electrochemical alkylation of Schiff bases¹⁰ has been studied to enhance their ability as a fuel for battery. However, so far no systematic electrochemical studies have been carried out on 3-[4'-(thiazolyl); 3-[4'-(acetyl)sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindoles.

Results and discussion

The synthesised 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindoles were subjected to electrochemical studies using cyclic voltammetry, coulometry, controlled potential electrolysis and spectrophotometry.

Linear sweep and cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammograms of 1.0 mM solution of 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethine indoles showed a well defined reduction peak at glassy carbon electrode in the

Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.0 to 12.0 (Fig. 1). In acidic buffers only one reduction peak appeared at and above the pH 4.5 and below this pH no peak could be realised, indicating that reduction of -CH=N- group is prominent in alkaline medium. In alkaline buffers (>pH 7.9) one additional $2e^-$ peak also appeared at higher cathodic potential which may be assigned to the cleavage of the C-N bond. The peak potential is found to be pH dependent and shifted towards more negative potential value with increase in pH.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 1.0 mM solution of 3-[4'-(thiazolyl)sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindole at different scan rate : (I) 50, (II) 100 and (III) 150 mV/s.

The involvement of hydrogen ion in the electrode process is confirmed by E_p vs pH plot. The break in this plot at pH 10.5 represents the pK_a value of the azomethine compound and corresponds to the association of hydrogen ions i.e. further increase in pH will not affect the number of protons involved in the reduction process. The electrochemical characteristics have been compiled in Table I. The cy-

Table 1. Electrochemical characteristics of 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindoles at various pH. $v = 50$ mV/s, conc. 1.0 mM

Sr. no.	R	pH	$(-E_p)_1/V$	$(-E_p)_2/V$	$(i_p)_1/\mu A$	$(i_p)_2/\mu A$
1.		5.6	0.80	-	1.6	-
		6.5	0.86	-	1.7	-
		7.9	0.94	1.20	1.5	1.6
		8.8	1.06	1.28	1.8	1.7
		10.5	1.10	1.32	1.6	1.7
		12.0	1.11	1.33	1.6	1.6
2.		5.6	0.75	-	1.4	-
		6.5	0.80	1.23	1.5	1.4
		7.9	0.88	1.27	1.5	1.5
		8.8	0.96	1.36	1.4	1.5
		10.5	1.08	1.41	1.5	1.4
		12.0	1.10	1.42	1.6	1.4

Table 2. Effect of concentration on peak current of 3-[4'-(thiazolyl)sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindole, pH, 8.8, $v = 50$ mV/s

Sr. no.	Conc. $\times 10^{-3} M$	$(-E_p)_1/V$	$(-E_p)_2/V$	$(i_p)_1/\mu A$	$(i_p)_2/\mu A$
1.	0.6	1.06	1.32	1.0	1.5
2.	0.8	1.11	1.34	1.3	1.5
3.	1.0	1.11	1.35	1.5	1.6
4.	1.2	1.13	1.37	1.9	1.7
5.	1.4	1.14	1.38	2.0	1.7

clic voltammograms of 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl] azomethineindoles were recorded in the concentration range 0.6 mM to 2.0 mM in aprotic medium. With increasing concentration peak potential shifted towards more negative value indicating diffusion controlled and irreversible nature of the electrode process.

Peak current (i_p) vs concentration plot in linear in lower concentration range which reflects the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction process and at higher concentration due to adsorption complications the plots deviate from the linearity. From the peak current values (Table 2) it is clear that the method is suitable for the estimation of 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethineindoles in the concentration range 10^{-2} to $10^{-4} M$. Cyclic voltammograms of the azomethines were also recorded at different scan rate from 50 to 250 mV/s to study the effects on the electrode process (Fig. 1). The peak current was found to increase proportionally with root of scan rate. A plot of i_p vs square root of scan rate is linear and passing through origin indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process.

Controlled potential coulometry :

Controlled potential coulometry (cpc) was performed to determine the number of electrons involved in the reduction process at different pH and it was found that below

pH 7.9 number of electrons in the electrode process is 2.0 ± 0.1 whereas above pH 7.9 it is 4.0 ± 0.1 .

Redox mechanism :

On the basis of cv, cpe, coulometry and spectrophotometric analyses, a mechanism has been postulated at glassy carbon electrode (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The effect of solvent composition on the voltammetric characteristics of 3-[4'-sulphonamoylphenyl]azomethine indoles were studied by recording cyclic voltammograms in dimethylformamide at pH 8.8 by increasing solvent concentration gradually from 40 to 70%. With increasing concentration of the solvent the peak potential shifted towards more negative potential value. In order to evaluate the effects of anions on the electrochemical behaviour, cyclic voltammograms were recorded in supporting electrolytes having a common cation and different anions (KBr, KI, KCl, KNO₃, etc.). No change in E_p and i_p was observed suggesting that anions do not affect the peak characteristics. With increase in the size of cations the E_p shifted towards more negative potential. Thus cations can only influence the electrical double layer at the electrode.

Experimental

The stock solutions ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) of the synthesised azomethines were prepared in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide, and other reagents were prepared using A. R. grade chemicals.

Equipment :

Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out on a potentiostat, Versastat EG & G II microprocessor based system. A three electrode cell was used for the purpose. To obtain cyclic voltammograms, glassy carbon electrode was used as working, saturated calomel electrode was used as reference and platinum wire was used as auxiliary electrode which was directly poured into the solution. The GC electrode was polished with fine grade emery paper followed by polishing alumina (0.5 μ m), washed and activated by triangular voltage sweeps from +1.0 V to -1.0 V at the scan rate of 5 and 200 mV/s for five minutes.

Controlled potential electrolysis (cpe) and coulometric studies were carried out on BAS CV-27 voltammograph in connection with digital electronic Omnigraph x-y/t recorder. A three electrode cell was used for the purpose. For coulometric determination, 1.0 mL solution of depolarizer having buffer, solvent to prevent precipitation and support-

ing electrolyte was electrolysed by the application of a potential slightly more than the peak potential. From the decrease in current or increase in coulombs with time the number of electrons transferred during course of reaction was calculated.

The cyclic voltammograms were recorded by mixing 1.0 mL stock solution of depolarizer, 1.0 mL of 1.0 M KCl, 2.0 mL of *N,N'*-dimethylformamide and 6.0 mL of appropriate buffer. For maintaining the inert atmosphere a stream of nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for about ten minutes. Redox reactions were followed by recording UV-visible spectra at different time intervals during the course of electrolysis.

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